

WHAT KEEPS ME GAMING: A NARRATIVE EXPLORATION ON ONLINE GAMING MOTIVATORS AMONG FILIPINO MILLENNIALS

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What Keeps Me Gaming: A Narrative Exploration on Online Gaming Motivators among Filipino Millennials

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Abstract

The swift evolution of modern technologies brought rapid advancements that led to the development of diverse forms of media that define the contemporary world. Among these, online games emerge as an influential trend that is leading the way in today's entertainment and interaction. This qualitative research aimed to determine the online gaming motivations of Filipino millennials, along with its connection to their gaming preferences and gaming continuance. The participants of the study were twelve (12) Filipino millennials who play online games, are currently employed, and residing in the National Capital Region. A semi-structured interview was used to collect data which was then analyzed through narrative thematic analysis. This resulted in nine major themes that encapsulate the gaming motivations of Filipino millennial gamers. The results show that the participants' primary motivations are the influence of their social environment, availability of gaming devices, appeal of gaming features, and use of gaming to cope. Moreover, their gaming preferences were also explored through reward systems, storyline, and game style. It was found that their initial gaming motivations were also the same drives for their continued gaming engagement. Essentially, Filipino millennial gamers consider gaming as a significant part of their lives. The implications of the study recommend propositions in education, career development, and counseling.

Keywords: *online games, online gaming motivations, gaming preferences, Self-Determination theory*

Introduction

Over the past years, cybertechnology has rapidly improved, redefining communication and entertainment. Gaming, particularly online gaming, is at the forefront of this change—with an estimated 2.7 billion players worldwide and around \$300 billion in revenue (Accenture, 2021). Existing literature support that playing online games has grown to be a part of our daily lives (Barbon, 2021; Fuster et al., 2012; Reyes, 2020; Turgut & Yaşar, 2019). Apart from a growing number of players, the gaming industry has boosted Filipinos' job opportunities in game development, testing, and customer support (Guevara, 2023). With its increasing popularity, most studies seek to determine the benefits and risks of online gaming but the reasons behind why individuals immerse themselves in these games remains underexplored, especially in the local setting.

Demetrovics et al. (2011) argued that the popularity of games is due to fulfilling basic needs, hence, these cannot simply be categorized as either good or bad. In this view, gaming can be explored through a motivational lens, prompting a focus on gamers' motivations behind playing. Motivation, as defined by Ryan and Deci (2017), “concerns what “moves” people to action” (p. 13). It deals with what energizes and gives direction to a certain behavior. With this in mind, the study primarily seeks to answer the research question, “What are the motivators of online gaming among Filipino millennials?”

The literature on gaming motivations is limited in the Philippines, with most studies conducted in countries such as Spain, Canada, and Turkey. (Fuster et al., 2012; Harper, 2020; Turgut & Yaşar, 2019, 2019). Local studies about online gaming directly correlate their findings to online gaming addiction (Barbon, 2021; Reyes, 2020). Thus, this lack of research on Filipinos' gaming motivations is a significant gap in the field. This also includes looking at this qualitatively as most of the studies available share a quantitative perspective. Since this topic is relatively new, the study may contribute to establishing Filipino gamers' gaming characteristics which may help subsequent studies in further investigating online gaming.

This research seeks to add to the dearth of literature in the field of online gaming in the Philippines. It specifically would like to explore the different factors that motivate millennials to play games online. The findings of the research may reveal a “profile” of Filipino millennials who are motivated to play online games, particularly in an in-depth exploration of their narratives. It can also be significant in various fields. First, in the field of psychology, play is found to have an important role in the development of a child in many areas, including cognitive, physical, and social—as suggested by psychological theories (Malhotra & Bholra, 2013). This is not limited to traditional play as research suggests that online games also promote development in a child such as improved brain intelligence (Rosyati et al., 2019). Aside from these, play is also a type of therapy mostly given to children with mental health problems or difficulties in similar areas (Rye, 2008). Online therapy emerged especially during the pandemic and thus, understanding online gaming motivators can contribute to planning interventions for online play therapy. Aside from therapy, the research may also contribute knowledge on gamification in education. Given the population of the study, the research can also aid in career development especially since their gaming experiences, choices, and preferences are explored in relation to their motivations. This study sheds light on how these factors interplay and potentially impact both personal growth and professional development, offering insights into the relationship between gaming and career advancement among Filipino millennials.

The findings of the study may contribute to the further study of problematic gaming in which culture-specific information and

interventions may be developed from the data that may be generated in this study. It may also be helpful for game developers in conceptualizing online games that can specifically cater to the Filipino audience as well as to add to the limited available resource in the field of business and marketing, to effectively develop strategies in branding and marketing these online games.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study is to explore the gaming motivators of Filipino millennials who play online games, with a focus on understanding the reasons behind their engagement and sustained involvement in these games. Specifically, the study will (1) identify what motivates Filipino millennials to play online games; (2) reflect on the role of their gaming preferences in their motivation for online gaming; and (3) explore their game continuance based on their identified gaming motivation. In pursuit of the study, the following research questions are aimed to be answered: what motivates Filipino millennials to play online games, how do these motivators relate to their gaming preferences, and how does their identified gaming motivation influence their gaming continuance?

Literature Review

Online Gaming

Due to its increasing popularity, the gaming industry has grown rapidly over the years (Anitha Rajathi & Ravisankar, 2022; Cheah et al., 2022; Shi et al., 2019). According to Clement's (2022) report, the gaming sector dominates the global digital media market, generating \$21.1 billion in revenue in 2020, which is a 21.9% increase from the previous year. This growth is attributed to the COVID-19 pandemic, which has prompted individuals to stay indoors and shift to digital entertainment. Presently, there are approximately 1 billion online gamers worldwide, and it is expected to increase to over 1.3 billion by 2025. These numbers suggest that the gaming industry is rapidly evolving and combined with the continuous innovations in technology, it is expected that this industry will continue to thrive in the coming years. Consequently, many studies attempt to further understand online gaming, especially in terms of how it affects the individual.

The rise of the internet greatly shaped our way of living. It has transformed the way we communicate, learn, work, and access information. Aside from these, the internet has also opened a bigger space for entertainment such as play. In agreement with this, Malhotra and Bolha (2014) share that the internet modernized the idea of traditional play as presented by psychological theories. Digitization of play can be evident in the emerging phenomenon of online games, referring to video games that can be played through a network, commonly over the internet (Anitha Rajathi & Ravisankar, 2022). The study will use this definition of online gaming and this will be interchangeably used with the terms video games and internet games.

Game Aspects

This study will explore how the participants' gaming preferences relate to their motivation to play. Given the wide range of elements that can comprise games, gaming preferences will be limited to the gaming aspects of what games the participants play. One of the gaps in online gaming motivation studies is also the lack of studies on gaming types (Demetrovics et al., 2011; Lafrenière, et al., 2012). This problem occurs as a game can be classified on overlapping game types. To address this, the current study will not be limiting its scope to a specific game type and would instead focus on the aspects of their chosen game.

Chang (2015) presented a list of gaming aspects based on previous literature which will also be adopted in this study. Among these gameplay aspects, reward system, game storyline, and game style are considered since these can be related to established theories on gaming motivations such as the Self-Determination Theory and Yee's (2006) motivations of play model. The reward system is characterized by how the game gives positive experiences to the player. These are comprised of eight subcomponents, namely scores, experience points, item granting, resources, achievement system, feedback messages, plot animations and pictures, and unlocking mechanism. This can be related to the extrinsic motivation of SDT and the achievement subcomponent of Yee's model.

The game storyline will revolve around the narrative or overarching theme of the game, which can be related to the immersion subcomponent of Yee (2006) and to SDT's autonomy for choosing the game's story progression, competence for challenges brought by the story, and/or relatedness for the storyline's facilitation of connections among the characters. Finally, the game style involves the interactivity of the gameplay, which highlights SDT's relatedness component since this aspect includes competitive (players strategize to oppose other players), cooperative (players work together but outcomes are not necessarily distributed equally), and collaborative (players work together and all shares the results) gameplay.

Prior studies on gaming genres are often quantitatively assessed (Chang, 2016; Wohn et al., 2020) or associated with problematic gaming or IGD (Park et al., 2016; Han et al., 2020). For instance, Wohn et al. (2020) found that female players had higher levels of external game regulation than males, in contrast to previous studies that men are more likely to play for achievement than women.

Khan et al. (2015) found that among 18,627 multiplayer online battle arena (MOBA) game players and 18,819 massively multiplayer online (MMORPG) game players, 63.8% of MOBA players were more motivated by competition than 33.7% of MMORPG players. This suggests that gamers with different motivations may play specific types of games. This will be explored in the study in terms of the aforementioned aspects since gaming types are difficult to differentiate since they can be combined.

Online Gaming Motivations

Studies on online gaming motivations can be dated back to the study of Bartle (2005) on player styles. In his proposed player-type model, he hypothesized that motives are related to four playing styles: achievers, explorers, socializers, and killers. Achievers are motivated to play because they like to win while explorers prefer to interact and discover in the virtual world. Socializers are driven to play because they can spend their time with their co-players in contrast to killers who like to bully or annoy other players (Bartle, 2005). After that, Yee (2006) tested Bartle's model empirically and found that 10 motivational components—particularly advancement, mechanics, competition, socializing, relationship, teamwork, discovery, role-playing, customization, and escapism—simultaneously describe the gamers' characteristics. With the limited game type studied by Yee (2006), Demetrovics et al. (2011) developed the Motives for Online Gaming Questionnaire (MOGQ), a scale to measure online gaming motives that encompass a wider range of game types. Similarly, Lafrenière et al. (2012) developed the Gaming Motivation Scale (GAMS), which was based on the Self-Determination theory. This will also be a theory to be used to guide the current research. Further, the MOGQ focused on the goals of gaming whereas the GAMS measures underlying motivations of gaming exclusively.

Dichotomous Views on Online Gaming

In investigating this phenomenon, top searches would immediately reveal the advantages and disadvantages of online gaming. The potential effects of online gaming have been a largely researched and debated topic. Most of the studies on online gaming present its risks and negative consequences, which often revolve around loss of control that may further lead to problematic gaming, addiction, and gaming disorder as identified by WHO. One study found that certain types of games have a higher risk for IGD due to more time spent playing the game (Han, 2020). Likewise, research has indicated that extended periods of play are associated with diminished psychological well-being, heightened levels of depression and anxiety, strained familial connections, and inadequate sleep (Chamarro et al., 2020; De Pasquale et al., 2020; Goh et al., 2019). However, it is important to note that these findings focused on excessive time spent on gaming, and thus, an adequate amount of play should not be assumed to be leading to these negative consequences.

In line with this, local studies have demonstrated a keen interest in exploring the disadvantages of online gaming. Two quantitative studies investigated the risk factors associated with Internet Gaming Disorder (IGD) among Filipino students (Barbon, 2021; Reyes, 2020). Findings in both of the studies suggest that agreeableness, a personality trait, is a significant risk factor for developing online game addiction. Other local studies focused on the effect of online gaming on the academic performance and attitudes of Filipino students (Garnada, 2020; Verecio, 2018). The studies aimed to predict the occurrence of IGD among Filipinos, as well as its effect on them. However, the researcher finds it lacking the foundation of its significance aside from frequent use. Thus, the establishment of the issue can be improved by looking at why Filipino gamers participate in this activity which is one of the objectives of this study. Although IGD is important and relevant to explore, it somehow immediately puts online gaming in a bad light—that it is always corresponding to video game addiction.

On the other hand, there are studies that suggest that playing online games also has potential benefits in various areas including cognition, motivation, emotion, and social aspects (Granic et al., 2014), as well as improving sensory and executive skills (Sahi & Bhagat, 2019), and psychological well being in adults (Allaire et al., 2019); however, these positive attributions to online gaming are typically overlooked due to the negative stereotypes associated with it. That being said, the researcher would like to explore gaming motivations without focusing on the opposing sides of online gaming. Instead, having a better understanding as to why gamers start and continuously engage in online gaming diminishes the bias one has towards gaming. Moreover, qualitative studies are lacking, especially in the local literature. A number of quantitative studies have established rating scales to measure motivations in online gaming such as the Motives for Online Gaming Questionnaire (MOGQ) (Demetrovics et al., 2011), Gaming Motivation Scale (GAMS) (Lafrenière et al., 2012), and even contextually made scales for Spanish gamers (Fuster et al., 2012). Conducting a qualitative study can deepen the understanding of online gaming motivations as some emerging themes may be identified aside from those provided in the gaming motivation scales.

Methodology

Research Design

A qualitative methodology with a narrative design was used for the study to explore and understand the meaning individuals attribute to their experiences (Creswell, 2014). Specifically, it captures the underlying motives of online gamers behind their engagement in online gaming.

Furthermore, a narrative approach was employed to delve into online gamers' narratives and investigate their motivations for playing online games as their gaming lifestyle was also inquired. This approach allowed the researcher to obtain rich information from the participants' perspectives and life experiences as to why they started and continue to play online games.

Participants

A total of 12 individuals, six males and six females, were selected as the final participants of the study. Initially, 48 individuals were interested in participating, however, some did not pass the criteria and failed to respond to the invitation. There were also four

participants who were interviewed but experienced technical problems that prevented the researcher from accessing their data.

The participants were Filipino citizens living in the National Capital Region who were born between 1981 to 1997 (the birth year of Millennials according to Chandan (2019)), currently employed, and play online games. The age range of selected participants is reflective of the data by Statista (2021) wherein most video game users were Filipinos aged 25 to 34 years old.

This is also because most of the studies available on online gaming have been saturated with student participants and thus the study investigated the experiences of those in the working class. As stated by PricewaterhouseCoopers (PwC) (2011), the millennial generation is distinguished by its affinity with technology. They were born with widespread access to digital technologies and the internet. In particular, millennials were also the first generation to grow up gaming, which led them to form a deep connection to gaming, making them some of the most engaged gamers in the present (Activision Blizzard Media, 2021). Furthermore, in a survey conducted by PUBLiCUS Asia Inc. in the Philippines last 2019, 4 in 5 millennials, aged 23 to 28, play online games. Based on the survey, 81.6% play online games out of 1,200 millennials asked (ABS-CBN News, 2019). From the data provided, it would be interesting to determine the gaming motivations of Filipino millennials given their early exposure and high prevalence of online gaming.

To ensure that the participants fit the criteria, interested individuals filled in a Google Form during the screening procedure before proceeding to the actual interview. In terms of the gaming criteria, they should:

Spend at least 7.5 hours per week playing online games

Be engaged in gameplay either through playing competitively, spending for in-app purchases, participating in online gaming forums/communities, or streaming

The study utilized a purposive sampling technique in selecting participants who were interviewed. Nikolopoulou (2022) defines this as a non-probability sampling technique in which participants are chosen based on specific characteristics or knowledge they have that are essential for answering the research questions of the study. This was used as the participants needed to meet certain criteria before participating in the study.

Instrument

A semi-structured interview was conducted to gather data from the participants. This type of data collection method uses a prepared set of interview questions; however may not be followed in order or verbatim (George, 2022). Open-ended questions were also asked to draw out the personal views and opinions of the participants (Creswell, 2014). After the construction of interview questions, the interview guide was validated through pilot testing which was done with two potential participants. After the pilot testing, no questions were removed but some were refined to enhance clarity. Appendix B provides the list of the interview questions asked of the participants.

Procedure

Participants were selected through the posting of publication materials in online gaming groups on social media. Interested participants then filled in a Google Form to ensure that they met the inclusion criteria for participation. The filtered participants were contacted to decide on their availability and preferred schedule for the interview. At the same time, informed consent was provided.

The interviews were held through Google Meet and one-on-one semi-structured interviews were conducted using open-ended questions aligned with the research objectives. With permission from the participants, interviews were recorded and then transcribed which was followed by the analysis of data.

Data Analysis

In analyzing the data gathered, a narrative thematic analysis, primarily based on the study of Butina (2015), was followed. This type of analysis is used to focus on the content within the text. It is composed of five stages: (1) organization and preparation of data, (2) obtaining a general sense of information, (3) coding phase, (4) identifying themes or categories, and (5) interpretation of data. The first stage involves transcribing the data and non-narrative dialogues and participant identifiers were removed. In this stage, the researcher arranged the transcripts in a Google Sheet to form a codebook. Afterwards, coding occurred where transcripts were reread followed by highlighting recurring ideas and emerging patterns to develop the codes. Next, the codes were analyzed and organized to form the major themes and subthemes. These themes were reflective of the major findings of the study. Finally, interpretation of the data occurred by deriving meaning from the data. Member checking was also done which involved going back to the participants to check for the accuracy and validity of the interpreted data. The final themes and subthemes were validated by four of the participants. Minor revisions were made including changes in word usage and spelling.

Ethical Considerations

The research study prioritized the autonomy of the participants. With this, the selected participants were asked to sign an informed consent form before proceeding to the interview. Before the interview, the participants were also asked for their consent to record the interview. Essentially, it also included their consent to voluntarily participate in the study. They also had the autonomy to discontinue their participation at any period of the study. Demographic information such as age, gender, and occupation was asked from the

participants but it was ensured that these could not be linked to their identity and the information they provided was kept confidential.

Results and Discussion

The main objective of this research is to explore the gaming motivations of Filipino millennials. The study aims to determine the factors that drive their interest and continued engagement in this type of online activity. The table below shows the general themes and subthemes that emerged from the data collected. Overall, nine primary themes were generated which were divided into three main parts that correspond to the research questions of the study. Particularly, these themes discuss the participants' (1) gaming motivations as well as their (2) gaming preferences and (3) gaming continuance in connection with their drive to play. Moreover, the table outlines the subthemes under each major theme which is explained further with sample narratives of the participants.

Table 1. *General Overview of Themes and Subthemes*

<i>Main Themes</i>	<i>Subthemes</i>	<i>Brief Descriptions</i>
Gaming Motivations of Filipino Millennials		
Influence of Social Environment	Gaming by recommendation	The participants started were motivated to play online games through the invitation and recommendation of their friends or family members.
	Gaming interactions for enhanced enjoyment	Having fun while playing with others is a motivation for most of the participants as games allow them to immerse in the game while interacting with fellow players.
	Gaming to explore social bonds	Being able to connect and interact with others in-game motivates the participants to play online games either with people online or with their friends, family, and significant others.
Availability of Gaming Devices	Access to device	Exposure to gaming devices motivated the participants to start playing online games.
	Aspiring to own personal gaming device	Witnessing others playing games on their own gaming devices prompted some of the participants to acquire their own device to be able to partake in gaming themselves.
Gaming Features	Aesthetics	The game aesthetics were a motivating factor for the participants particularly the character design, art style, graphics, and music of the game.
	Mechanics	Gaming mechanics refer to the general structure and rule system of the game. The participants were motivated by these mechanics as it enabled them to engage in games aligned with their preferences and acquire skills corresponding to the type of game they play.
	Progression	Game progression involves the advancement and development of the game. This drives the participants to further engage in gaming as they want to reach the game's conclusion and experience the entirety of the game's content.
Gaming as Coping	Gaming as stress reliever	The participants find gaming as a way to alleviate their stress, especially after their working hours. They perceive gaming as a tool for relaxation and a means to unwind after the demands of their daily life.
	Gaming as distraction and escapism	Online games also serve as a distraction for the participants as immersing in games diverts their attention from the difficulties of real life.
Gaming Motivations and Gaming Preferences of Filipino Millennials		
Reward System	Attain a sense of accomplishment	Playing online games to achieve rewards or milestones in-game motivates the participants. This gives them a feeling of satisfaction and competence through achieving or completing challenges or tasks integral to the game.
	Gain a sense of control	Exercising their authority in the gaming realm drives the participants to play. Making their own decisions and independently solving the game's missions enhances their experience which also contributes to their mastery and agency.
Storyline	Foster learning through game's narrative	The game's story motivates the players to engage in gaming to acquire new knowledge and skills since the games they often play depict true-to-life events.
	Reflect character connection to personal factors	The participants were found to establish a connection with their game characters at varying levels. This contributes to their drive to play as it adds to their gaming engagement and makes their gaming experience more meaningful.
Game Style	Build Connections	Online games, particularly multiplayer games motivate the participants to play given their capacity to fulfill the participants' need for social interaction and connection. The social aspect of online games allows them to interact with other people regardless of distance.
	Nurture existing relationships	Using games to strengthen the bonds that the participants currently emerged as a notable gaming motivation. They utilize games as a bonding activity, to maintain communication, and catch up with their friends and family.
Gaming Motivations and Gaming Continuance of Filipino Millennials		
Initial gaming motivations as a driving force to continue gaming	Primary motivation aligned with sustained gaming engagement	The participants were found to continue playing online games for the same reason why they started gaming.
	Gaming continuance evolved from primary	Aside from maintaining their primary motivations, the participants developed additional reasons to continue gaming which emerged upon playing the game.

motivation

Millennials allocate time to play despite work

Online gaming was revealed to be integrated into the lives of the participants as they dedicate time to play games despite their work and life responsibilities.

From the themes that have resulted in the study, a framework was made to also provide an overview of what had been found in the study. Figure 1 below shows the major themes integrated with the initial framework to guide the research. As shown, this framework is formed to the identification of online gaming motivations in relation to their gaming preferences and gaming continuance. The dotted line indicates that only some of these aspects were their reason for continuance while the solid line for gaming motivations and continuance implies that Filipino millennial gamers continue to play for the same reasons why they started gaming.

Figure 1. *Online Gaming Motivations of Filipino Millennials in Relation to their Gaming Preferences and Gaming Continuance*

Gaming Motivations of Filipino Millennials

One of the main objectives of this study is to determine the reasons why Filipino Millennials play games. It was found in the study that generally, participants play because of the influence of their friends or family, access to gaming devices, features of the game, and because they use gaming to cope.

Influence of Social Environment

The study results show that the primary gaming motivations of the participants were predominantly shaped by the influence of their social environment. Among the 12 participants, five of them were motivated to play due to this kind of influence. These social groups often include their family members, friends, and significant others. This influence extends to recommendations from these individuals, playing to share enjoyment with them and to seek more interactions with fellow gamers in the digital realm.

This main theme is aligned with SDT's relatedness component which was also evident in other studies that explore gaming motivations through this theoretical lens. Moreover, the social groups that were found to influence the participants were similar to the study by Rooij et al. (2017) that stated that children's motives were highly affected by parental and family attitudes, influences, and control but adults, which the participants of this study are considered under, are assumed to be more influenced by other family members or romantic partners with their gaming behavior. Additionally, close family ties drive teenagers to play with their family and friends to share their experiences in real-world relationships (Uz & Kagiltay, 2015). Similarly, this connection that started in their adolescence continued until adulthood which is observed with the participants of the study.

Gaming by Recommendation. A number of the participants engage in online games based on what has been recommended by them. They reveal that they begin to play the game by witnessing what others are playing and gradually being invited to join by other individuals. They have also shared that their game choice is significantly affected by what game has been introduced to them by others. MP9, a 26-year-old virtual assistant and player support, stated that he started gaming at an early age and this began through his friend's recommendations. He stated, "I was in grade 3 back then, the first encounter of my online games, basically it was because of my friends... naglaro sila ng online game, nagandahan ako, nagpaturo ako kung paano then 'yun na, I got hooked up." [Trans. I was in third grade back then, the first encounter of my online games, basically it was because of my friends... they played an online game, I found it interesting, I asked them how it was played, then that's it, I got hooked.]"

Gaming interactions for enhanced enjoyment. Additionally, participants are found to play online because they experience fun whenever they play games. Some have shared that they have their go-to playmates who they wait for to play together. Having shared that it is more fun to play with their friends, they also shared that their gaming becomes more immersive as they play with others. When MP12 was asked about the meaning of social interactions in online games, he stated that:

I find it meaningful kasi other than common, united goal, yung mga random banter, more fun, parang it enhances already the fun game lalo na pag may other people talking, ‘yung mga nag-jojoke, mag nag-aasaran. It is better as a whole pag may nangyayaring gano’n.

[Trans. I find it meaningful because other than having a common, united goal, the random banter, more fun. It’s like it enhances the fun game, especially when there are other people cracking jokes and teasing each other. It is better as a whole when things like that happen]

Along with this, the mere social presence of others in the game, even without interaction, interests the participant as well. Uysal and Yildirim (2016) impart that massively multiplayer online games (MMOs) provide interactions between the players which can facilitate relatedness needs. It was found in their study that relatedness and the other two components were positively linked with presence, enjoyment, and preference for future play. Relatedness in games is often associated with multiplayer games; however, single-player games in digital worlds and non-player characters (NPCs) which can make the player feel acknowledged and supported can satisfy relatedness needs as well (Rigby & Ryan, 2011).

Gaming to explore social bonds. Another subtheme regarding social influence in the participants’ gaming motivations involves online games as a platform to socially explore. This includes seeking new connections with other people in-game and gaining more awareness of relationship boundaries. According to MP11, he engages in online games to connect with others to look for attention which he finds to be lacking in real-life:

Marami kasi akong naging kaibigan so naghanap na rin kasi ako ng atensyon ng iba. So ayun, kaya ako nag-focus nga rin sa paglalaro kasi nga naghahanap ako ng atensyon. So ‘yun yung nag-attract sakin na mag-more of gaming na lang.

[Trans. I had a lot of friends so I also sought attention from others. That is why I focused on playing games because I am looking for. That’s what attracted me to do more gaming instead]

Despite this, it was also evident that compared to the male participants, most of the female players prefer to play solo due to stressful interactions that often happen in-game, one of which shared that it is preferable for games to have options that allow them to play with others or alone.

The results of the study are similar to most of the quantitative studies on gaming motivations which include the social component of games. These commonly involve getting to know new people, playing with and helping others, and forming meaningful relationships with others (Yee, 2006; Demetrovics et al., 2011; Lafrenière et al., 2012). Further, another quantitative research by Uz and Kagiltay (2015) also supports this study as the female participants also prefer to play single-player games. With regard to relationship boundaries, it was also notable in their study that gamers do not prefer sharing sensitive issues with friends they have made in gaming environments.

Availability of Gaming Devices

At a young age, most of the participants had early access to various gaming devices. Some were also compelled to play games because they witnessed some of their friends or family owning gaming devices. This drove them to approach their parents for similar access or purchase their own.

Access to Device. Two of the participants shared that their family owned a computer shop which allowed them to have easy access to such devices to play games while others had the opportunity to play because a family member of theirs had one. Some of them also stated that they visit computer shops during their high school days to play. FP1, an English tutor, is one of the participants who grew up around gaming devices who shared that, “before kasi when I was really young, ‘yung mom ko meron siyang internet café, silang dalawa ng college friend niya, tapos dati after nila ako sunduin doon muna nila ako dadalhin.” [Trans. Before when I was really young, my mom and her college friend owned an internet café. So after they fetch me, they bring me there first.]

She also added when asked about other platforms she played:

When I was little, hindi kasi kami super yaman nung bata pa ako, tapos meron akong pinsan na may kaya tapos siya yung tipo na meron siyang Atari, meron siyang Playstation gano’n, so everytime na ando’n ako sa kanila nilalaro namin ‘yun.

[Trans. When I was younger, we weren’t really wealthy, and I had a cousin who was well-off, and he had an Atari, he had a Playstation and stuff like that, so whenever I was at their place, we would play those.]

Aspiring to own personal gaming device. Some of the participants expressed their desire to own their own gaming device as they have witnessed other people have their own. As kids, they did not have the ability to buy their own so they would ask their parents to purchase for them; however, as they got older they felt that they had more independence to buy whatever device or game they want from their own money. MP10 told his story of wanting to have his own Playstation while FP6 conveyed her freedom to buy what she wants now as an adult.

Noong nakita ko yung Playstation sa bahay syempre nainggit ako, nagpabili rin ako and then fortunately my parents bought one, ayun ever since then I played with my cousins my sister, my friends sa Playstation. Hanggang sa syempre through out the years parang lumalao na siya, dumating yung mga PC games ganyan, so nagpabili nanaman ako ng PC. -MP 10

[Trans. When I saw the Playstation at home, of course, I felt envious, so I also asked for one, and fortunately my parents bought it. Ever since then, I played with my cousins, my sister, and my friends with the Playstation. As the years went by, it went outdated, then PC games aros, so I asked for a PC.]

Wala ka pang capacity no'n eh. Masyado ka pang bata. It's the adults who are dictating what they get for you at that time. Pero ayun since I can make my own choices, pag naiinggit ako sa iba, edi ok, bilhin ko nalang 'yan. Parang your independence come into play na rin do'n. -FP6

[Trans. You didn't have the capacity back then. You're still so young. It's the adults who are dictating what they get for you at that time. But now, since I can make my own choices, if I feel envious of others, then ok, I'll just buy it myself. It's like your independence comes into play there as well.]

The accessibility of devices among the participants served as an initial catalyst for them to begin their gaming journey which has endured through adulthood. Their desire to have their own device may stem from the need to belong which can refer to the relatedness component of SDT, as well. It is highlighted in the findings that autonomy also plays a role particularly as they grow older. With more purchasing power, they are able to freely choose the game they want to play as well as buy their own gaming device. This autonomous motivation reflects intrinsic motivation since they voluntarily engage in these activities due to their interest and enjoyment (Tam, 2021).

Gaming Features

This main theme mainly revolves around the common gaming features that motivate the participants to play: the game's aesthetics, mechanics, and progression. Despite the participants playing a diverse set of games, these general features are the common ones that drive them to play.

Aesthetics. It was discovered from the findings that participants value the overall aesthetics of the game. This revolves around the characters, graphics, and music of the game they are playing. Most of the female participants are motivated to play when there are visually appealing male characters in the game. Interestingly, music is also found to be an important feature of the game because it was found to evoke emotions during gameplay. Finally, the graphics and art style also push them to play due to their visual appeal and variations. FP2, a speech pathologist, shared the factors why she plays online games, sharing that, "One thing is because it is interesting. Two, as a child syempre eye-catching siya. Three, it lets you live in another world parang as a different character with added super powers, and number four kase pogi yung mga characters." [Trans. One thing is because it is interesting. Two, as a child, it's eye-catching. Third, it lets you live in another world, like, a different character with added superpowers. And fourth, the characters are handsome.]

Mechanics. The mechanics of the game is another important motivator for the participants as well. Although they do not play games with the same mechanics, it was generally found that the participants are motivated to play with the type of game mechanics they prefer. For example, there are those who are driven by strategic or logical mechanics, while others prefer those that are more relaxing such as world-building and map exploration. MP12 shares that he does not think of the game mechanics as much as long as he understands it.

Siguro, if I understand the mechanics right away, tapos that's the only thing that I need to play. Kase nowadays busy ka na sa work tapos pati ba naman game pag-aaralan mo?...pero from the most part if unknown game siya if I understand the mechanics siya, basta gets ko siya, di naman ako yung tipong na kahit card game siya or barilan, basta ma-gets ko.

[Trans. Maybe, if I understand the mechanics right away, and that's the only thing I need to play. Because nowadays, you're already busy with work, so would you still think about learning the game?... . but for the most part, if it's an unknown game, as long as I understand the mechanics, as long as I get it, I'm not the type who, even if it's a card game or a shooting game, as long as I understand it.]

Progression. Further, participants expressed that they are motivated to play and continue to do so because of the game's progression. They want to see through the end of the game or monitor how it would progress such as unlocking new levels, characters, or items. For instance, FP2 played Dragon Fable as one of her first games and she expressed how she was motivated to play due to the development of equipment of her dragon, in which she said, "ang nagustuhan ko na na-realize ko is syempre yung pag-develop ng dragon, kase 'yun yung pinaka-goal ko eh, 'yung mabago yung itsura ng dragon ko. Tsaka syempre paganda nang paganda yung equipment, 'yun yung nakakamotivate sa 'kin." [Trans. What I really liked that I realized is, of course, the process of developing the dragon, because that's my ultimate goal, to change the appearance of my dragon. And of course, when the equipment gets better and better, that keeps me motivated]

Gaming features are influential factors that guide gamers in their decision in choosing games. Choice, which is a significant interactive element in games, differentiates it from other forms of entertainment (Uysal & Yildirim, 2016). Autonomy needs are addressed in games that have more character customization or dialogue options which were features that were also available for the games that the participants play such as Genshin Impact and Mobile Legends. Research suggests that choices in games increase autonomy. It was observed that gamers who personalized their in-game characters exhibited stronger identification with their avatars, consequently fostering heightened autonomy, immersive engagement, invested effort, enjoyment, positive impact, and extended gameplay duration

(Birk et al., 2016).

Moreover, it can be posited that the participants exhibit intrinsic motivation toward the game's aesthetics and mechanics while the game's progression is more of an extrinsic motivator for them. The aesthetics provide them with positive stimulation so they engage in games itself, to enjoy and attain personal satisfaction. Similarly, mechanics allow them to explore the gaming world or be thrilled with the logical mechanics of the game. Sepúlveda (2020) recommends that games should have interesting mechanics that are complemented by visual components. Striking this balance in gameplay ensures that players feel motivated intrinsically rather than feeling obligated to do the game tasks. In contrast, extrinsic motivations are displayed by players who play to obtain in-game awards or to gain admiration and recognition from others (Lafrenière et al., 2012). This can depend however on the degree of internalization of individuals which can transform motivations from being externally regulated to being self-driven. This transition might arise from gamers finding satisfaction in understanding the game's conclusion, rather than solely focusing on the achievements they attained in-game.

Gaming as Coping

The participants are found to be drawn to gaming because it provides them relief from stress. Gaming serves as an escape from their life's difficulties as well. Immersing themselves in the virtual world provides them a temporary break from their concerns, allowing them to have some time to unwind and redirect their attention.

Gaming as stress reliever. Given that the participants are working individuals, most of them play online games to relax. They report that they consider gaming as their rest time after work or during their break time. One participant shared that they game to feel sleepy and another sought more relaxing and stress-free games which they often refer to as "chill" or "low maintenance" games. MP11 considers gaming as a relief to stress especially since he works as a call center agent who deals with difficult clients.

Hindi na siya past time eh, naging route ko na siya for stress reliever, lalo na sa work, sa buhay, sa everyday life ganun nga. So hindi ko na siya matanggal, so kaya more on sige laro pa rin kasi alam mo 'yon parang araw-araw ka ng minumura sa work dahil nga sa mga customers tapos syempre, hinding hindi naman mawawala yung problema, kaya yan mas nagiging motivated akong maglaro pa rin para mawala yung stress.

[Trans. It's not just a pastime. It has become my route for stress relief, especially with work, and everyday situations. So I can't really let go of it. That's why I continue to play more, you know, because every day at work you get cussed out by customers, and of course, problems will never disappear. So, playing games still motivates me further to alleviate the stress.]

As another way to decompress, some of the participants also shared that they play games as an inspiration for their creative output as some of them work in the creative field. The relaxation that game provide may also stem from the certain features it offers such as the satisfaction derived from overcoming challenges which leads to feelings of competence and social interactions which provide fun and enjoyment to unwind with other players. It was also noted that the players play for a long period of time which may suggest flow state. This mental state bears similarity to meditation, an action often done to reduce stress. Cruea (2020) provided similar findings in which video games were found to induce flow state that result to mindfulness by fostering relaxation, heightened focus, better mood, reduced stress, and increased empathy.

Gaming as distraction and escapism. Playing online games had been found to offer more than just relief from stress for the participants. FP2 labeled this experience as "disconnecting from the real world." For these participants, online games serve as a safe space for them, allowing them to distance themselves from the stress and exhaustion of their responsibilities in work and life. FP5, a 27 year-old online content writer, conveyed that "I play games is because it was enjoyable it distracts me from my tiredness and it relaxes me after work."

MP7, a 41-year-old media practitioner and e-sports advocate, provided another perspective on gaming as an escapism. He shared that games similarly work with society through a quote, "Someone's patriot is another man's terrorist," in that the roles we take and perceive depend on a personal level. Similarly, he shared that the meaning of games differs for every person, and for him, games allow you to be who you want to become.

What I will say probably won't be the same as the other ones pero yung meaningful ko kasi sa game kasi, is an escape to be who you want to be in another situation. Where you can be either a hero or a villain. Kasi ang maganda ngayon binibigyan ka na ng option while ethics may tell you otherwise, pero ngayon kase binibigyan kana ng option na kahit hero ka masama ugali mo. No'ng time namin di ka pwede maging masama ang ugali.

[Trans. What I will say probably won't be the same as the other ones but the meaning I find in games is it's an escape to be who you want to be in another situation. Where you can be either a hero or a villain. The interesting thing now is that you're given the option, while ethics may tell you otherwise, but now, you have the option that even as a hero, you can have a bad attitude. During our time, you couldn't have a bad attitude.]

Gaming literature often explores positive and negative effects which suggests gaming like a double-edged sword. Determining whether it leans toward positivity or negativity is still inconclusive. The study of Desai et al. (2021) suggests that casual video games can be an effective medium for reducing stress which was similar to the findings of the study. They added that the accessibility, user-friendliness,

and popularity of casual games make them a promising instrument for stress management.

Despite these, it is also acknowledged that even though video games are accessible tools for coping with difficult life experiences, they are not always beneficial because it is greatly dependent on a person's life circumstances (Pallavicini, et al., 2022). Monley et al. (2023) explained that video games are designed to fulfill the basic psychological needs wherein gamers experience a sense of control, skill, and connection to others when they play. However, problematic gaming may arise when those with unmet needs solely rely on video games to meet them. Additionally, research found that gamers may experience a momentary sense of well-being which can potentially serve as an outlet for real-life frustrations. Nevertheless, an overreliance on this approach could increase the likelihood of developing problematic internet use (Chang et al., 2018).

Gaming Motivations and Gaming Preferences of Filipino Millennials

The next three major themes revolve around gaming preferences of Filipino millennials. These themes discuss how the participants' motivations to play related to their gaming preferences. A study by Chang (2015) was used to have a general flow of the interview questions which were then reflected in the themes as well. These three gaming aspects are reward system, storyline, and game style.

Reward System

The reward system refers to the in-game rewards that are usually offered in games. This could come in the form of scores, experience points, equipment or items, and unlocking mechanisms.

Attain a sense of accomplishment. The participants report that they are motivated by the reward systems that the games that they play offer. Commonly, this involves ranking systems and defeating opponents to gain specific rewards such as new or rare equipment, skins, or alike. These participants share that when they achieve something, it fosters a sense of anticipation and eagerness to achieve more accomplishments. This had been expressed by MP8, a 27-year-old teacher who mostly plays Mobile Legends, stating that "ang hirap makuha yung Mythic pero yung eagerness na ma-achieve ko yung rank na mythic, 'yun yung nag-pupush sa akin na patuloy maglaro." [Trans. It's challenging to reach Mythic rank, but the eagerness to achieve that rank is what pushes me to keep playing.]

Despite these, four out of the 12 participants do not care much about rewards in games because they prefer other aspects such as the storyline and some believe that these only push them to spend more money to unlock these types of rewards. FP6 stated that she continues to play the game because she has already invested time and money. She also expressed her overall thoughts on in-game rewards:

Nako, nakakademonyo 'yang in-game rewards na 'yan. So ayun nga, lalo na pag nagsisimula ka pa lang diba you feel na you need to spend more kasi you need to meet that particular tier or minimum amount or kung ano man. It's only pag nag accumulate na tapos tinignan mo na yung bills mo or diba sometimes they have the history ng transaction that's only when you realize na, I fell into the trap.

[Trans. Oh, those in-game rewards are tempting. Especially when you're just starting out, you feel like you need to spend more because you have to meet a particular tier or a minimum amount, or whatever it may be. It's only when you've accumulated a certain amount and you look at your bills, or sometimes they have a transaction history, that's when you realize, "I fell into the trap."]

Gain a sense of control. Another factor that drives participants to play in the context of rewards is the sense of empowerment they get from feeling in control over the game that they play. They perceive themselves as gaining a higher level of autonomy in making decisions. This volition, in turn, fuels them to be more persistent in achieving the objectives of the game. When FP5 was asked about her most satisfying gaming experiences, according to her:

My particularly satisfying moment is definitely when I played games na may sneaky concepts. I just like thinking, and I like hiding, also kase pag mag fight head on, I really like being able to think what to do next, being able to plan it out, I guess because it gives me a sense of control.

[Trans. My particularly satisfying moment is definitely when I played games with sneaky concepts. I just like thinking, and I like hiding, also when there is a fight head-on, I really like being able to think what to do next, being able to plan it out, I guess because it gives me a sense of control.]

As aforementioned, reward systems motivate gamers extrinsically as they receive different forms of rewards and accomplishments. Specifically, this pertains to external regulation, encompassing gratification derived from acquiring currency, items, unlocking game elements, gaining experience points, reaching certain levels, or attaining recognition as a good player (Lafrenière et al., 2012). Similar to these findings, a study by Cruz et al. (2015) on badge systems in video game consoles found that badge systems can boost motivation, elevate enjoyment, engagement, and time spent for interested players. Likewise, completionists feel immense satisfaction when all badges are earned and feel frustration if not, which indicates that its effect also varies based on the gamers' level of investment. These types of rewards also satisfy competence needs as they promote mastery through the completion of challenges and achievement of goals.

Moreover, gaining a sense of control imparts the satisfaction of autonomy needs because their in-game decisions are self-endorsed and they feel control over their choices. This may be driven intrinsically or extrinsically but Ballou (2020) asserts that autonomy is different

from independence in which other's decisions are not considered. Plenty of choices do not indicate autonomy as well but the choices made should be meaningful for the gamer.

Storyline

Secondly, the game's narrative also plays a role in the participants' motivation. This aspect relates to the story progression, challenges brought by the story, as well as the connection towards the characters of the game. In connection to their primary motivations, the storyline had been evident in their preferences towards the gaming features, particularly the graphics or art style and characters.

Foster learning through game's narrative. The narrative aspect of games is found to facilitate learning particularly in storylines that portray real-life events or situations close to reality. The exposure and familiarity from such narratives result in the acquisition of knowledge about the history and culture of other countries.

Additionally, four of the participants who work in the academic field reported that games contribute to the learning process. This observation hold potential for gamification in education as they report that they use some of the game elements such as the story to connect with their students. Aside from this, participants believe that games help them to learn and develop skills. This includes improving their cognitive skills and strategic thinking as well as enhancing their communication skills and learning English. FP4 shared that one of her motivations to play stems from being able to learn while playing, "again, Assassin's Creed. They're really big on history kasi even though it's fiction, it's somehow relevant pa rin on what happened to the real world. Kaya ako na-momotivate rin kasi it's something to learn also." [Trans. Again, assassin's creed. They're really big on history because even though it's fiction, it's somehow still relevant to what happened in the real world. That's why I am also motivated because it's something to learn also.]

Aligned with these findings, studies have demonstrated that immersive learning environments currently integrate storytelling elements such as how digital game-based learning integrates stories for students to learn more efficiently (Naul & Liu, 2020). The same study discovered that distributed narratives, intrinsic integration of fantasies, empathetic characters, and responsive elements encompass effective characteristics of game narratives. Game narratives were also found to promote immersion, engagement, motivation, and learning which can explain the findings of the study.

Moreover, in the motivation spectrum, learning from games can come from identified regulation as this drives individuals to develop important aspects and develop abilities significant to them (Lafrenière et al., 2012). In particular, these are the skills and aspects they can use in their daily lives, especially in their jobs. Research found that gaming allows players to acquire different soft skills based on their job categories which can assist them in their career development. For instance, their study revealed that managers displayed preference for action roleplay games, allowing improvement in organizational and planning skills. Notably, one of the participants also shared the same skill she learns from the game she is playing.

Reflect character connection to personal factors. Most games involve characters that you need to control. Upon asking if they felt any connection with the in-game characters they play, three of the participants indicated a lack of significant attachment to the story or the character they play. Conversely, among those who feel a connection, a difference in their level of connection is observed. The majority of these participants primarily relate to the struggles the character is facing; however, some simply regard them as an inspiration, others feel empathetic towards the character while there are also those that immerse themselves in the role that the character has. For MP11, he relates to the role he has to accomplish in the game:

It is beyond of the character it is more of the role. Halimbawa yung role ng pagiging tank, na va-value ko siya kapag nakikita ko na laging siyang character na parang bugbugin, tapos hindi siya nagiging MVP, pero sobrang importante niya. Ta's yung connection pag nag-tatank ako, nararamdaman ko na I need to protect them, na parang ako muna unahin niyong bugbugin para maka-take sila.

[Trans. It goes beyond the character, it is more about the role. For instance, the role of being a tank, I value it when I see that this character is always getting beaten up, yet doesn't become the MVP, but is incredibly important. The connection that comes when I'm tanking is when I feel that I need to protect them, like I should be the one to take the attacks so they can strike.]

The character connection that had been found in the study entails more than controlling the character. Erb et al. (2021) also found that player-character relationships can go beyond the mechanical control of the character that is to project oneself to the role of the game's story. This connection is also referred to as player-avatar relationship (PAR) which is understood in a four-point typology that outlines the level of socialness and motivations situated in a continuum (Banks, 2015). This supports the differences between the gamers' level of relationship aside from the mechanics of the game which could also influence this relationship.

The player-avatar typology is related to the motivational concepts of competence, relatedness, and autonomy as well. For instance, avatar-as-object highlights the competence of the player, considering the avatar as a mere tool for combat and competition. In this type of relationship, there is little regard for interpersonal social relationships where the player is detached and merely uses the avatar for strategic gameplay. This approach disregards the avatar as a unique digital entity—prioritizing the game objectives over social interaction and expression of identity. This is exemplified by FP2's relationship with her avatar which she expressed that she chooses a character that relates to her personality, that is, preference over classes like ranged fighters or tanks. She shared that she was impatient and using these certain classes allows her to attack immediately, even without the help of teammates. Furthermore, some of the relationships that the participants have formed cannot be neatly categorized in these relationships due to limitations in exploring these

relationships as it was a new and unexpected finding. To illustrate, the other participants expressed empathetic feelings toward their avatar which may be seen as an Avatar-as-Other Relationship. However, they also connect their personal experiences with their avatar's experiences, resembling elements of Avatar-as-Symbiote Relationships. Although, they did not integrate their avatar's persona in their real lives rather they only found likeness in their experiences such as their life struggles. This complexity suggests that further studies could further investigate these unique relationships that may be in between or extend beyond the established categories.

Game Style

The last major theme in exploring the gaming preferences of Filipino millennials regarding their motivations is the game style. This aspect underscores the social dynamics within online games, often discussed in various modes such as collaborative, cooperative, or competitive. Two distinct subthemes surface from this area wherein participants either play to form new relationships or cultivate and strengthen existing ones.

Build Connections. As aforementioned, the influence of social groups was significant for the participants in playing online games. In further exploring this, it was also found that their gaming engagement extends to the desire to meet new people. The social features in games allow participants to interact with other people regardless of their location. Four of the participants expressed that they were able to establish friendships with individuals from distant countries, with whom they still remain in contact, and such event involve MP9 expressing that, "you build friendships, the people you don't know, the people miles away. The farthest I have built in-game was from US and India. They are very rare."

Interestingly, the four participants who teach said that they use games to connect with their students. This bridges the gap between the generation since most of their students play online games. They described games as conversation starters and a means for engaging and getting the interest of their students. FP3, a 32-year-old teacher in a private industry, shared that she used games like Mobile Legends to motivate one of her students who had trouble accomplishing his worksheets and attending their class:

I used mobile legends for example to connect to what they have to do in the center... Okay this is what we are going to do. So you are going to come to the center more often. You can play a game before you come inside tas pag natapos kana pwede ka na umuwi. If you are not going to do anything else from school kasi okay naman school works niya, edi tsaka ka mag-game ulit. So every time na tapos na siya dito, imbis na umuwi muna siya, mag-one game muna siya bago umuwi. So 'yun 'yung compromise namin with the mom so atleast nagagawa na niya 'yun.

[Trans. I used mobile legends for example to connect to what they have to do in the center... Okay this is what we are going to do. So you are going to come to the center more often. You can play a game before you come inside then after you finish, you can go home. If you are not going to do anything else from school if you're done with school works, then you can play again. So every time that he's done with our tasks, he can play again before going home. That's the compromise with his mom. At least this works for him.]

Nurture existing relationships. In addition to forming new connections, the study also revealed that the participants play online games to nurture their relationships with their current friends or partners. These participants shared that they belong to groups that they often play with. These interactions bring them a sense of satisfaction especially when they work toward shared goals or when there is humor involved. Further, some shared that it is important for them to consider their friend's or partner's preferences in choosing the games that they play. Moreover, they perceive these in-game interactions as a means to catch up and create deeper relationships with one another. MP10 shared that these interactions help his friends and him to still be updated with one another despite their busy schedules:

...kasi kapag naglalaro kami, we just don't talk about the game, we talk about our lives and kamusta na and all that, so parang in a way, nagiging way siya to catch up kasi syempre sa age ko ngayon, may mga anak na rin and all that, kumbaga day to day di na talaga kame nag uusap eh...

[Trans. ...because when we play, we just don't talk about the game, we talk about our lives, how we're doing, and all that. So, in a way, it becomes a means to catch up because, at my age now, some of us already have children and all that, so we don't really get to talk anymore every day...]

Despite this, four of the participants also state that they often prefer to play solo. This is due to their personal preference but three of them also expressed that the toxicity of some Filipino gamers contributes to this. Rather than dealing with these types of gamers, they choose to play alone instead.

As discussed in the primary gaming motivations of the participants, the social component in games is a factor that drives them to play. Besides external influences, their drive also stems from the desire to form new relationships or strengthen the current ones. Yee (2006) presented three main motivations to play: achievement, immersion, and social components. In his work, the social component includes getting to know other players as well as deepening relationships with others. Research suggests that social motives are crucial in switching modalities that pertain to integrating online friendships to offline and vice versa (Domahidi, 2014). It was found that online gamers who had stronger inclinations to seek social connections and teamplay were more likely to meet online friends personally. They were also more likely to integrate their offline friends into the game which allows them to spend more time together and strengthen their relationships. Finally, Erikson's psychological stages state that after establishing relationships with others, individuals focus on contributing to society and forming families. As millennials belong to the latter stage, this clarifies their inclination to engage with

familiar acquaintances rather than forming new relationships while playing. This can explain why they prefer to play with those they know instead of making new connections.

Gaming Motivations and Gaming Continuance of Filipino Millennials

The final set of themes derived from this research predominantly pertains to the participants' motivation in connection to their gaming continuance. It was discovered that only two of the participants think that their initial gaming motivation and why they continue to play are different. Conversely, the remaining ten maintain the same motivations to play or they had some additions. The study also emphasizes the integration of playing online games among Filipino millennial gamers.

Initial gaming motivations as a driving force to continue gaming

The majority of the participants have been gaming for more than ten years and this research would like to investigate whether their original motivations persist as reasons for their continued engagement in games. From this section, two subthemes emerged with an equal number of participants with five each. First, these participants were consistent with their initial motivation while the other participants also have consistent motivations but with additional factors that push them to play up until now.

Primary motivation aligned with sustained gaming engagement. The participants who had consistent motivations from the time they started gaming stated that they continue to play due to the influence of their friends and family, curiosity towards the game's story progression and mechanics, and availability of the gaming device particularly now that they are able to purchase their own. FP1 shares that she continues to play similar to why she started which is to play with her friends and family:

I think it is similar kasi I mentioned my cousin earlier, and I also mentioned I started playing Genshin to relate to my sister so I think those are also my motivation kasi gusto ko talaga yung aspect of gaming these days na you are connecting with other people especially since the pandemic started.

[Trans. I think it is similar because I mentioned my cousin earlier, and I also mentioned I started playing Genshin to relate to my sister so I think those are also my motivation because I really want the aspect of gaming these days that you are connecting with other people especially since the pandemic started.]

Gaming continuance evolved from primary motivation. Of the participants who had additional reasons as to why they play games, the majority of them have shared that aside from their primary motivations, they now play to be relieved from stress. The factors that add to their gaming continuance are also a realization after they learn more about the game that they are playing. For instance, MP8 stated that:

Same pa rin walang nagbago. Wala ako makita ibang dahilan para magtulak sa 'kin para magtuloy. Nand'on pa rin ako sa graphics, influence, siguro dadagdag ko diyan 'yung fulfillment na nararamdaman ko kapag nag-MVP ako. Kapag tumataas 'yung rank ko gan'on.

[Trans. It's the same, nothing changes. I don't see another reason to motivate me to continue playing. There is the graphics, influence, but I would also add the fulfillment I feel whenever I am the MVP. When I am promoted to a higher rank.]

Among the participants, reasons for their gaming continuance vary but are related to their initial gaming motivations. This suggests that as a player's satisfaction increases, their intention to continue playing also increases, and they are more inclined to play more frequently (Putzer et al., 2020). This is in accordance with the uses and gratifications theory which proposes that players are satisfied with different elements of gameplay. Likewise, this can be applied to the current research where the participants retained their primary motivations which indicates that they persist in playing because it enables them to fulfill their needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness. Considering that their additional motivation was to be relieved from stress, which may not be directly related to the satisfaction of their needs, this could be influenced by their personal circumstances instead.

Millennials allocate time to play despite work

Lastly, it was found that gaming is already a part of the daily routine of Filipino millennial gamers. Most of them work in a hybrid set-up and they report that, with a more flexible mode, they are able to play even during their working hours. Those who are unable to do so, try to cram their gaming during their break time. When asked about their gaming routine, most stated that they engage in gaming simultaneously with their other tasks such as when they eat or tending to household chores. MP9 shared that he plays when work is not too busy, "pinagsasabay ko siya actually, pag minsan di naman kasi gano'n kabigat trabaho ko on both works. Kaya nga sila, napagsabay ko rin silang dalawa. Ngayon 'yung dalawa kong work pag wala masyado ginagawa do'n ako naglalaro." [Trans. I actually do them at the same time especially when the workload isn't too heavy for both jobs. That's why I manage to balance the two. Now, when I don't have much to do in either of my two jobs, that's when I play.]

The pandemic changed people's lifestyles in many ways. One of which is that it has increased screen time and consumption of digital media, especially online gaming and related activities (Claesdotter-Knutsson et al., 2022). Most of the participants work from home allowing them to play during their break time or unoccupied time. A study by Rupp et al. (2017) investigated the affective and cognitive abilities of casual video games which were compared to a guided relaxation activity. The results show that those who engaged in the

casual video game demonstrated greater involvement and affective restoration than those in the relaxation condition. This could imply why millennial gamers have incorporated gaming into their daily routine, particularly since some of them use games for work-related purposes or to recharge for upcoming tasks.

Overall, the findings of this study suggest that Filipino millennial gamers can be motivated by different factors but mostly revolve around similar ones from existing literature such as the social, achievement, and immersive components from Yee's (2006) gaming motivation model. This similarity is reflected as both studies utilized the SDT as a theoretical basis. Generally, it appears that the participants were motivated to play online games to satisfy their basic psychological needs of competence, relatedness, and autonomy. The need for competence is satisfied through playing games to achieve rewards, controlling their characters, and completing strategic game tasks that emphasize mastery over the game. Additionally, online games are known for their multiplayer features which address the relatedness needs of the participants. From starting their gaming engagement through the influence of their social groups, the participants were also motivated to play to meet new people and fortify their existing relationships with friends and family. Lastly, autonomy needs are met through character customization and decision-making within games, granting the participants a sense of control over the games that they play. These findings demonstrate that the satisfaction of these needs serves as driving forces to start and continue engaging in online games. In essence, this suggests that the fulfillment of psychological needs plays a crucial role in igniting and perpetuating the engagement of the participants in online games.

Moreover, there are also unique findings from the study such as gaming from recommendations and availability of devices. The research also found that the purchasing power of millennials greatly affects their motivation to play. Now that they have more autonomy and means to buy their own, they are more driven to engage in gaming. Some of the participants expressed their desire to buy the games they wished for as a kid which springs the experience of nostalgia for them as they have experienced playing older games. Finally, the older participants also impart that they want to promote responsible gaming, especially for the youth. They expressed that parents should not stop their children from gaming; however, should be balanced with their studies and other responsibilities.

Conclusions

The advancement of technology provided opportunities for more kinds of digital entertainment to emerge, one of which is online gaming. The results show that Filipino millennial gamers are motivated to play online games due to the influence of their social environment, availability of gaming devices, pull of gaming features, and utilization of games to cope. Gaming was found to be an integral part of the lives of Filipino millennial gamers. Despite their work and life responsibilities, they pursue gaming and dedicate time to play amidst their busy schedules. Playing online games keeps the child in them, allowing them to reduce their stress, keep their minds sharp, and strengthen their social bonds.

In addition, the findings of this study contribute implications for various fields such as education, career development, and counseling. A major takeaway from this study is that gamers are able to learn from the game's story. This highlights the potential of gamification in the academic field. Games may be used for teachers to connect with students and make their lessons more interesting through the incorporation of games. Educators may use narrative game elements to engage students in learning which may be best conducted with the integration of digital technologies as well. Moreover, the results also suggest that millennial gamers also gain skills that they can use at work and in their daily lives. Thus, knowing their motivations may help working individuals make more intentional choices in terms of choosing games. They may also align their gaming choices with their personal goals to enhance their skills. Ultimately, this can promote maximization of time and resources as well as a healthier work-life balance in the industry. Companies can also consider using games as relaxation techniques or as an engaging activity for collaborative tasks. Similarly, the study recognizes the potential of games as online therapeutic strategies to alleviate stress. Counseling plans may be integrated with gamification elements that facilitate meditation or healthier coping strategies. While more prevalent in education, gamification is gradually extending into mental health practices. With this, mental health professionals could start to acknowledge the potential of games as a therapeutic tool to keep up with the advancement of e-mental health. This can involve using online games as a meditation activity by evoking a flow state, as implied by the study, or by immersing in sensory stimulation which games can offer.

Also, now that gaming disorder has been classified under the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-11) and is recognized by the World Health Organization as a disorder (De Pasquale et al., 2020; Harper, 2020), and Internet Gaming Disorder, as a condition that needs further study under the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders 5th edition, findings may support current management and strategies in dealing with the condition. Culture-specific interventions may likewise be developed given the data that will be generated in this study.

References

ABS-CBN News. (2019). 4 in 5 millennials play online games-survey. <https://news.abs-cbn.com/business/04/21/19/4-in-5-millennials-play-online-games-survey>

Accenture. (2021). GAMING: the next super platform. https://www.accenture.com/_acnmedia/PDF-152/Accenture-Gaming-Article.pdf

Activision Blizzard Media. Growing up gaming: meet the millennial gamers. (2021).

<https://www.activisionblizzardmedia.com/insights/blogs/2021/q2/growing-up-gaming--meet-the-millennial-gamers>

Allaire, J. C., McLaughlin, A. C., Trujillo, A., Whitlock, L. A., Laporte, L., & Gandy, M. (2013). Successful aging through digital games: Socioemotional differences between older adult gamers and Non-gamers. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 29(4), 1302–1306. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2013.01.014>

Allen, J. J., & Anderson, C. S. (2018). Satisfaction and frustration of basic psychological needs in the real world and in video games predict internet gaming disorder scores and well-being. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 84, 220–229. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2018.02.034>

American Psychiatric Association. (2013). Internet Gaming Disorder. https://www.psychiatry.org/File%20Library/Psychiatrists/Practice/DSM/APA_DSM-5-Internet-Gaming-Disorder.pdf

Anitha Rajathi, V. M., & Ravisankar, S. (2022). A study on the impact of online games to the academic performance of the students in Tamilnadu (Dharmapuri district). *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, 3(6). <https://ijrpr.com/uploads/V3ISSUE6/IJRPR5363.pdf>

Ballou, N. (2020, April 1). Self-determination theory in video games: misconceptions about basic psychological needs. <https://nickballou.com/blog/sdt-in-video-games-basic-needs-misunderstandings/>

Ballou, N., Deterding, S., Iacovides, I., & Helsby, L. (2022). Do People Use Games to Compensate for Psychological Needs During Crises? A Mixed-Methods Study of Gaming During COVID-19 Lockdowns. In CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3491102.3501858>

Banks, J. (2015). Object, Me, Symbiote, Other: A social typology of player-avatar relationships. *First Monday*. <https://doi.org/10.5210/fm.v20i2.5433>

Barbon, W.E. (2021). Some factors associated with video game addiction of Filipinos found during the COVID-19 pandemic. <https://www.dlsu.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/pdf/conferences/research-congress-proceedings/2021/SEP-13.pdf>

Bartle, R. (2015). Multi-User Dungeons (MUDs). *The International Encyclopedia of Digital Communication and Society*, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118767771.wbiedcs009>

Birk, M. V., Atkins, C., Bowey, J. T., & Mandryk, R. L. (2016). Fostering Intrinsic Motivation through Avatar Identification in Digital Games. *ACM Digital Library*, 2982–2995. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2858036.2858062>

Butina, M. (2015). A Narrative Approach to Qualitative Inquiry. *Clinical Laboratory Science : Journal of the American Society for Medical Technology*, 28(3), 190–196. <https://doi.org/10.29074/ascls.28.3.190>

Chandan, H. C. (2019). Technology, learning styles, values, and work ethics of millennials. In *Advances in logistics, operations, and management science book series* (pp. 892–903). <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-7362-3.ch067>

Chang, H. Y., Poh, D. Y., Wong, L. L., Yap, J. Y., & Yap, K. Y. (2015). Student Preferences on Gaming Aspects for a Serious Game in Pharmacy Practice Education: A Cross-Sectional Study. *JMIR medical education*, 1(1), e2. <https://doi.org/10.2196/mededu.3754>

Cheah, I., Shimul, A. S., & Phau, I. (2021). Motivations of playing digital games: A review and research agenda. *Psychology & Marketing*, 39(5), 937–950. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mar.21631>

Chamarro, A., Oberst, U., Cladellas, R., & Fuster, H. (2020). Effect of the frustration of psychological needs on addictive behaviors in mobile videogamers—the mediating role of use expectancies and time spent gaming. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(17), 6429. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17176429>

Claesdotter-Knutsson, E., André, F., & Håkansson, A. (2022). Gaming Activity and Possible Changes in Gaming Behavior Among Young People During the COVID-19 Pandemic: Cross-sectional Online Survey Study. *JMIR serious games*, 10(1), e33059. <https://doi.org/10.2196/33059>

Clement, J. (2022). Online gaming. *Statista*. <https://www.statista.com/topics/1551/online-gaming/#topicOverview>

Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. Sage.

Cruea, M. D. (2020). Gaming the mind and minding the game: mindfulness and flow in video games. *Video Games and Well-being: Press Start*, 97-107.

Demetrovics, Z., Urbán, R., Nagygyörgy, K., Farkas, J., Zilahy, D., Mervó, B., Reindl, A., Ágoston, C., Kertész, A., & Harmath, E. (2011). Why do you play? The development of the motives for online gaming questionnaire (MOGQ). *Behavior Research Methods*, 43(3), 814–825. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13428-011-0091-y>

De Pasquale, C., Sciacca, F., Martinelli, V., Chiappedi, M., Dinaro, C., & Hichy, Z. (2020). Relationship of Internet Gaming Disorder

- with Psychopathology and Social Adaptation in Italian Young Adults. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(21), 8201. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17218201>
- Desai, V., Gupta, A., Andersen, L., Ronnestrand, B., & Wong, M. (2021). Stress-Reducing Effects of Playing a Casual Video Game among Undergraduate Students. *Trends in Psychology*, 29(3), 563–579. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43076-021-00062-6>
- Domahidi, E., Festl, R., & Quandt, T. (2014). To dwell among gamers: Investigating the relationship between social online game use and gaming-related friendships. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 35, 107–115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2014.02.023>
- Fuster, H., Oberst, U., Griffiths, M. D., Carbonell, X., Chamarro, A., & Talarn, A. (2012). Psychological motivation in online role-playing games: A study of Spanish World of Warcraft players. *Anales De Psicologia*, 28(1), 274–280. <https://ddd.uab.cat/pub/artpub/2012/128933/anales.pdf>
- Garnada, V. (2020). Online gaming addiction and academic attitudes: The case of college students in the Philippines. *International Review of Humanities and Scientific Research*, 417–426. <https://irhsr.org/papers/1542279612.pdf>
- George, T. (2022). Semi-structured interview definition, guide & examples. Scribbr. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/semi-structured-interview/>
- Goh, C., Jones, C., & Copello, A. (2019). A further test of the impact of online gaming on psychological wellbeing and the role of play motivations and problematic use. *Psychiatric Quarterly*, 90(4), 747–760. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11126-019-09656-x>
- Granic, I., Lobel, A., & Engels, R. C. M. E. (2014). The benefits of playing video games. *American Psychologist*, 69(1), 66–78. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0034857>
- Guevara, R. (2023). Gaming in the Philippines: From pastime to mainstream entertainment. M2.0 Communications Inc. <https://m2comms.com/2023/02/17/gaming-in-the-philippines/>
- Han, H., Jeong, H., Jo, S. J., Son, H. J., & Yim, H. W. (2020). Relationship between the experience of online game genre and high risk of Internet gaming disorder in Korean adolescents. *Epidemiology and health*, 42, e2020016. <https://doi.org/10.4178/epih.e2020016>
- Harper, C. D. (2020). Motivational factors of online gaming in intermediate elementary. *Leadership Research*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.25316/IR-15250>
- Joseph, P., & Winston, K. (2022). What is exploratory research? Study.com. <https://study.com/learn/lesson/exploratory-research-overview-design-examples.html>
- Kahn, A. S., Shen, C., Lu, L., Ratan, R., Coary, S. P., Hou, J., Meng, J., Osborn, J. C., & Williams, D. (2015). The Trojan Player Typology: A cross-genre, cross-cultural, behaviorally validated scale of video game play motivations. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 49, 354–361. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2015.03.018>
- Lafrenière, M. K., Verner-Filion, J., & Vallerand, R. J. (2012). Development and validation of the Gaming Motivation Scale (GAMS). *Personality and Individual Differences*, 53(7), 827–831. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2012.06.013>
- Malhotra, R. & Bhola, K. (2013). Playing games: a qualitative study on online gamers. *Indian Streams Research Journal*, 4(8). https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2497963
- Monley, C. M., Liese, B. S., & Oberleitner, L. (2023). Gamers' and non-gamers' perspectives on the development of problematic video game play. *Current Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-023-04278-w>
- Naul, E., & Liu, M. (2019). Why story matters: A review of narrative in serious games. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 58(3), 687–707. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0735633119859904>
- Nikolopoulou, K. (2022). What Is Purposive Sampling? | Definition & Examples. Scribbr. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/purposive-sampling/>
- Park, J. Y., Han, D. H., Kim, B. N., Cheong, J. H., & Lee, Y. H. (2016). Correlations among Social Anxiety, Self-Esteem, Impulsivity, and Game Genre in Patients with Problematic Online Game Playing. *Psychiatry Investigation*, 13(3), 297. <https://doi.org/10.4306/pi.2016.13.3.297>
- Patton M.Q. 2002. *Qualitative research & evaluation methods* (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Patzer, B., Chaparro, B., & Keebler, J. R. (2020). Developing a Model of Video Game Play: Motivations, Satisfactions, and Continuance Intentions. *Simulation & Gaming*, 51(3), 287–309. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1046878120903352>
- PricewaterhouseCoopers. (2011). Millennials at work reshaping the workplace. <https://www.pwc.com/co/es/publicaciones/assets/millennials-at-work.pdf>

- Reyes, M. R. (2020). Risk factors of internet gaming among Filipino students. *Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews*, 8(4), 230–237. <https://doi.org/10.18510/hssr.2020.8424>
- Rupp, M. A., Sweetman, R., Sosa, A. E., Smither, J. A., & McConnell, D. S. (2017). Searching for Affective and Cognitive Restoration: Examining the Restorative Effects of Casual Video Game Play. *Human factors*, 59(7), 1096–1107.
- Ryan, R. M., Rigby, C. S., & Przybylski, A. K. (2006). The Motivational Pull of Video Games: A Self-Determination Theory Approach. *Motivation and Emotion*, 30(4), 344–360. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11031-006-9051-8>
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2017). Self-Determination Theory: Basic Psychological Needs in Motivation, Development, and Wellness. In Guilford Press eBooks. <https://doi.org/10.1521/978.14625/28806>
- Rosyati, T., Purwanto, M. R., Gumelar, G., Yulianti, R. T., & Mukharrom, T. (2020). Effects of Games and How Parents Overcome Addiction to Children. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(1), 65–67. <https://www.jcreview.com/index.php?mno=302645135>
- Rye N. (2008). Play therapy as a mental health intervention for children and adolescents. *The journal of family health care*, 18(1), 17–19.
- Sahi, M. & Bhagat, G. (2019). Positive effects of online games: a review. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 6(8), 60-70. <https://www.jcreview.com/admin/Uploads/Files/61a4723e6c4002.43511818.pdf>
- Sepúlveda, F. (2020). Visual aesthetics in video games and their effects on player motivation [Master’s thesis, Northeastern University]. Northeastern University Library. <https://repository.library.northeastern.edu/files/neu:m0455d134>
- Shi, J., Renwick, R., Turner, N., & Kirsh, B. (2019). Understanding the lives of problem gamers: The meaning, purpose, and influences of video gaming. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 97, 291–303. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2019.03.023>
- Tam, F. (2021, March 15). Understanding motivation in games – Self-Determination Theory. LinkedIn. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/understanding-motivation-games-self-determination-theory-frankie-tam>
- Turgut, M., & Yaşar, O. M. (2019). Playing Digital Game Motivations of University Students. *Asian Journal of Education and Training*, 5(4), 603–608. <https://doi.org/10.20448/journal.522.2019.54.603.608>
- Uz, C., & Cagiltay, K. (2015). Social interactions and games. *Digital Education Review*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/280805543_Social_Interactions_and_Games
- Verecio, R. L. (2017). Online gaming addiction among BSIT students of Leyte Normal University Philippines and its implications towards academic performance. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.17485/ijst/2018/v11i147/137972>
- Wohn, D. Y., Ratan, R., & Cherchiglia, L. (2020). Gender and genre differences in multiplayer gaming motivations. In *HCI in Games: Second International Conference, HCI-Games 2020, Held as Part of the 22nd HCI International Conference, HCII 2020, Copenhagen, Denmark, July 19–24, 2020, Proceedings 22* (pp. 233-248). Springer International Publishing.
- Yee, N. (2006). Motivations for play in online games. *CyberPsychology & Behavior*, 9(6), 772–775. doi:10.1089/cpb.2006.9.772
- Yee, A., & Sng, J. R. H. (2022). Animal Crossing and COVID-19: A qualitative study examining how video games satisfy basic psychological needs during the pandemic. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.800683>

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